

USE OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING MUSIC THEORY

Ibrakhimjanova Gavkhar Amanbayevna

International Nordic University

Associate professor of the "Music education" department

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10012043>

Abstract: This article reveals the importance of musical theoretical analysis in the development of students' musical literacy. There is also detailed information about the methods of musical analysis.

Key words: musical education, theory, analysis, educational system, musical signs.

Introduction.

The formation of concepts related to music literacy in music lessons is of special importance. Because the child learns about elementary music literacy in the elementary grades at school. It is not an exaggeration to say that this situation is particularly evident in the form of music. After all, music samples are becoming our companions in our daily life. At the same time, there are a number of complicated-looking situations in our cultural life in connection with samples of music at different levels and levels and their various performing arts. Musical literacy plays an important role in the formation of musical culture by helping students to understand music. At this point, it is necessary to consider that the musical instrument is also important in the piece of music being played. Because it is possible to test the theoretical concepts learned in musical instruments.

We can see our national chogs, which have been formed for centuries and have an important place in the spiritual life of our people, being used in various ensembles and creative teams (orchestras), even by Estrada groups in new interpretations. All this testifies to the rich timbre and breadth of technical capabilities of our national musical instruments. At the same time, the selection of repertoire in the performance of our national instruments is the cause of many discussions. The subject of music theory, the ability to apply theoretical concepts of music theory in music lessons, has not been researched.

Theoretical analysis is important in the implementation of musical literacy. In the process of performance education, the main task of the teacher is to teach students the knowledge and skills necessary for performance. Exercises to develop the ability to read a sheet of music fluently. Cultivating inner hearing, the concept of musical texture, the principle of "I see, hear, play", teaching to read the text of the sheet music in a comprehensive way, getting to know the text of the sheet music for the first time, the shape, general direction, dynamics and analyzing its specific aspects. Internal auditory skill is to harmonize the text of the musical score and the auditory skill of performance on the instrument. Practical mastering of the most common application options and types of invoices. Analyzing a piece, identifying a musical phrase, distinguishing meters and methods. Musical sentence and its connection with speech. An important part of working on a work is to understand its content correctly. Ways to determine musical expressions, the importance of proper breathing in performance.

Dynamics - author and editor dynamics as a means of artistic expression, types of dynamic change. Common pitfalls in performing dynamic characters.

Musical method is one of the main features of musical speech. Features of mastering complex methods. Pauses in musical performance. The relationship between the general character of the work and the level of speed, the use of raetranom. Name the speed of the work. Learning musical accompaniment. Features of heating with jornavoz. If the student is properly taught to read sheet music and analyze the text, then the skill of the musician in the future is the factor of the perfect performance of the musical piece.

When working on a piece of music, musical literacy is very important, and it is impossible to analyze the work without musical literacy. Acquaintance with the musical work, mastering the text, methods of memorizing it, what to pay attention to while memorizing it. Artistically correct interpretation of music. It implies the formation of high moral and aesthetic consciousness, respect for work and similar qualities in students. Understanding the character, tonality, artistic image direction, climax and structure of your music will help you to perform well in the future. After theoretical mastery of Asami, it is transferred to its practical performance. Music works are not of the same technical difficulty from beginning to end, although some parts of it may be more difficult to perform than others. In this case, it is recommended to isolate these difficult areas and perform special exercises on them. Even if this difficult part can be performed smoothly by the performer independently, in many cases the same part can be isolated without joining the general direction of the asami during the performance of the asami from beginning to end. Therefore, when repeating a difficult part, it is recommended to add a few beats before and after this verse.

When mastering the piece, it is necessary to choose a speed that is suitable for the performer's capabilities and to achieve a rhythm at this speed. Knowing how to properly work on music is one of the factors of improving performance skills. The main goal of working individually in the class is to get acquainted with the general content of the musical instrument, to master the performance skills used in it, and to be able to interpret the musical experience that is to be expressed on the basis of this with the help of the instrument. The limitation of the time allotted for mastering individual pieces of music means the acceleration of the process of working on this work, the student has the task of mastering certain material in a short, limited time. This gives every student the opportunity to get acquainted with new materials, not to stay in one place, and not to repeat the previous materials in the same way. The important thing is that the works chosen for the class work should be liked by the students and arouse great interest in them. Effective use of classroom work is important in expanding the student's listening experience and professional aspects of the musical worldview. Improving performance skills in the educational process is one of the main factors for the general musical development of students.

Composer's skill is the factor of complete performance of musical works. Individual approach to each student in improving performance skills. Work on sound quality. Applying the "Simple to Complex" principle of inner hearing that develops the skill. In developing musical skills, independent education is very important in addition to individual lessons. In terms of independent thinking, the student should not follow the teacher's instructions and opinions without being sure, but one should be able to express one's personal attitude on an issue through performance. The student's conscious attitude to the art of music performance plays a leading role in independent training. Some teachers are overly patronizing to their

students and encourage them to work independently. On the contrary, the earlier the opportunity is created for students to work independently, the faster its results will be visible. Gamma and etudes are very important in developing the musician's performance skills, and working on various exercises helps the musician and the student to improve the student's technical capabilities and performance skills. But it should not be forgotten that the performance of gamma and triad should be aimed at a specific goal. It is very important for the teacher to choose works according to the student's ability to perform, and the choice of gamma etudes to develop the ability to perform.

Gamma and arpeggio playing techniques on an instrument are basic material to learn by practicing. It is known that they are widely used in all areas of music performance. Learning gammas and arpeggios at the beginning of the elementary school period helps to acquire and strengthen the position of the fingers through the left hand, to acquire the bars, to move from one string to another and to change positions, and later on to play and artistically helps the performer in learning the technique of sound production.

Thus, using gamma and arpeggio for musical exercises is the most accurate and short way to develop performance techniques. For this purpose, the pedagogue should be able to interest the pupil or student, as well as convince him with the experience of playing, as well as with examples taken from very different works.

The use of new innovative technologies in improving music literacy gives good results, they are:

- *Free and independent thinking;*
- *Be comfortable in the team;*
- *To expand the scope of knowledge;*
- *To play musical notes well;*
- *To develop speech and communication culture;*
- *Affects the knowledge of musical elements and meaningful expression.*

The advantage of these methods is that if the student cannot perform theoretically and practically, the people next to him will help, the teacher will demonstrate the performance, and the student will not hear many reprimands. Before we use these methods in our lesson, we need to explain to the students of the group how to carry out, start and the essence of each method. In order for each method to come out completely and clearly, the question we ask should be clear and focused on one goal.

It should be noted that by teaching music theory and literacy to elementary school students, we will be able to increase students' musical theoretical knowledge. Organization of the creative process related to music theory in music culture classes is necessary to ensure that the theoretical foundations of teaching students to think creatively in music education are mastered from a practical point of view and to develop the activities of singing according to notes in music classes more productively and at a higher level.

References:

1. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" // People's word. - Tashkent, 2020. - September 24. - B. 1-2.
2. Concept of pedagogical education of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - Tashkent: UzR XTV, UzPFITI, 1995. - 20 p.

3. Muslimov N.A. Professional formation of future vocational education teachers. Tashkent, Science, 2004
4. Abdullaeva Q.M. Methodological foundations of formation of professional knowledge and skills of future teachers in teaching special subjects: Dis. ... ped. science. nom. - Tashkent, 2006. - P. 182.
5. Muslimov N.A. Design activity of the future teacher. 2012. Study guide. 6.1 b.t.
6. Panjiev Q.B. Art of Uzbek folk singing. Study guide. Tashkent, 2021. - P. 274.
7. Tolipova J. Requirements for the competence of teachers. Methodical manual. Tashkent: Science and Technology, 2010. - P. 125
8. Kholikov A.A. Pedagogical skills. Monograph. Tashkent: Economy and Finance, 2011. - P. 418.
9. Hoshimov K., Nishonova S. History of pedagogy: Textbook. - Tashkent: National Library of Uzbekistan named after Alisher Navoi, 2005. - P. 304.
10. Panjiev Q.B. Improvement of professional training of future music teachers by means of Uzbek folk singing. Monograph. T.: Makhalla and family publishing house. 2021. – 200
11. Panjiyev Qurboniyoz Berdiyevich “UZBEK SEASONAL CEREMONY” European Journal of Innovation in Nonformal Education Vol. 2 No. 4 (2022): European Journal of Innovation in Nonformal Education <http://innovatus.es/index.php/ejine/issue/view/14>
12. Panjiyev Qurboniyoz Berdiyevich “COMPONENTS FOR IMPROVING THE PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF FUTURE MUSIC TEACHERS” International Journal of Pedagogics Vol. 2No. 04 (2022); <https://theusajournals.com/index.php/ijp/>

